

Motivative Factors of Professional Self-Realization of the Person

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Abstract: *Neuropsychologists pay much attention to career guidance for young people who are faced with the challenge of choosing the profession. Numerous studies on motivation and professional determination prove the need to identify individual features of the brain organization of mental functions in the context of psychological support for the educational process at school and career guidance. Neuropsychological research indicates the links between the predominant activity of a certain hemisphere of the brain and professional realization in certain areas. The empirical study was conducted using reliable and valid psycho-diagnostic techniques (“Questionnaire of professional self-realization” by O. M. Kokun (2014; 2016); the “Motivational profile” technique by S. Richie, & P. Martin (2004); correlation analysis). At the stage of qualitative analysis, two groups of subjects with different levels of professional self-realization were identified (using the «ace» method). A visual analysis of the motivational factors profile structure in groups with high and low levels of professional self-realisation demonstrated differences in the graphs configuration and their location, and also provided an opportunity to characterize the psychological motivation characteristics of representatives of each of the groups. Against the general background of communicative self-sufficiency, adaptability and self-confidence, in a group of persons with a high level of professional self-realisation, the dominant motives are constant improvement, recognition by others. Representatives of a group with a low level of the studied phenomenon are interested in the motives of good working conditions and high wages. It has been proved that persons with different levels of professional self-realization differ in the specificity of the dominance of motives.*

Keywords: *personality, self-realization, professional self-realization, non-psychological mechanisms of motivation, career guidance, motivational factors, correlation analysis.*

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Introduction

The relevance of the problem of the professional self-realisation of an individual is conditioned, on the one hand, by the significant economic and, as a consequence, professional changes taking place in the modern world, and, on the other hand, by the subjective ideas of the individual about the specifics of self-change, self-realisation in a certain profession.

The analysis of scientific research indicates that the gradual mastery of professional skills encourages a person to use not only psycho-physiological resources, but also potential personal capabilities, self-achievement, self-change, self-transcendence, self-development, self-actualization, purposeful application of professional knowledge, skills and abilities that lay the foundations for further development subjectivity in the profession (Kokun, 2015, p. 14; Nerubasska et al., 2020; Nerubasska & Maksymchuk, 2020; Palamarchuk et al., 2020).

From the point of view of Maksimenko & Osedlo (2011), the basis for effective professional activity of a person is the opportunity to realize oneself in creative work. But, unfortunately, the motives of a person's labor activity are often not the desire for self-actualization through creative work, but the desire to satisfy their biogenic and sociogenic needs of a lower order. Therefore, it is very important to discover the psychological conditions for the professional self-realization of the individual, i.e., how much a person sees the personal meaning in his professional activity (Maksimenko & Osedlo, 2011, p. 3).

Solving professional tasks enables a person to satisfy the need for self-realization, self-actualization, to make the fullest use of personal potential, thereby increasing the prospects for professional self-realization (Bolshakova, 2012, p. 104). It becomes vital for every future professional to constantly improve oneself, to search for new opportunities for realizing one's abilities and one's personal potential (Lukina, 2006, p. 17). Developing his professional skills and abilities, a person gradually realizes his own importance in the profession, sees himself as an initiative and responsible person, treats himself as a value, identifies and realizes the most important motives for himself. The totality of internal motivating elements of a person, such as needs, interests, values, constitutes a person's motivation in the profession. Under the influence of hierarchically built motives, a person gradually forms an attitude towards the activity performed and a program of behavior in it. A person's motivation increases due to an increase in the ways of realizing his own motives in the profession, which leads to the possibility

of real influence on the reasonable organization of his further personal and professional self-realization.

A neuropsychological approach follows the theory of systemic and dynamic localization of higher mental functions. It was developed by Luriya (1973), the founder of national neuropsychology. Nowadays, neuropsychology attempts to identify the brain factors shaping behaviour and facilitating understanding and motivation to achieve goals and ways to do it. Both neuropsychology and psychophysiology have significantly enriched knowledge about the psychological foundations of motivation towards cognitive activity. Early identification of neuropsychological causes behind learning difficulties allows psychologists and educators to determine levels of higher mental functions, identify strengths and weaknesses of mental development in the early stages (from early childhood) to elaborate the most effective strategy for further pedagogical support and correction.

Many scholars have made attempts to analyze the use of neuropsychological methods in educational institutions and determine assessment criteria and approaches to correcting learning difficulties (Akhutina & Pylaeva, 2015; Semenovich, 2008; Khokhlov & Slovenko, 2020). Their findings prove that neuropsychological methods are an adequate means of identifying strengths and weaknesses of functional systems and specify neuropsychological predictors affecting educational attainment. Besides, some researchers (Korsakova et al., 2017) claim that successful and unsuccessful children differ in levels of praxis, memory, acoustic gnosis, spatial functions, language, attention and thinking. At the same time, attention and mental activity disorders act as the most specific for underachieving pupils. Insufficient development of other functions is individual in nature and cannot be considered as a natural combination of dysfunctions in case of academic failure.

Leading research covers both psychological and non-psychological mechanisms of motivation. Indeed, Gore & Zweifel (2013) and Trifilieff et al. (2013) reveal a neurobiological and neuropsychological understanding of motivation. Others devote their studies to the purposeful selection of actions. At the same time, Bailey et al. (2015) offer a strategy for disclosing purposeful actions and affecting components of motivated behaviour.

Neuropsychologists pay much attention to career guidance for young people who are faced with the challenge of choosing the profession. Numerous studies on motivation and professional determination prove the need to identify individual features of the brain organization of mental functions in the context of psychological support for the educational process at school and career guidance. Neuropsychological research indicates the

links between the predominant activity of a certain hemisphere of the brain and professional realization in certain areas. For one, Arshavskiy (2001) explains how pupils with the dominance of left or right hemispheres master exact sciences and humanities. In particular, pupils with the left hemispheric type response show great success in exact sciences and pupils with the right hemispheric type of response in humanities.

In this context, Stepanov (2008; 2013) believes that it is important to consider the style of perception and processing of information, typical of people with the dominance of left or right hemispheres when choosing the profession. Left-hemispheric cognitive style is characterized by the predominance of the verbal and logical processing of information, analyticity, specification, succession and abstractiveness. At the same time, the right-hemispheric cognitive style involves similar processing of information, as well as syntheticity, integrity, simultaneity, specificity and intuitiveness. The researcher believes that “the stable dominance of right-hemispheric cognitive style indicates natural inclinations to a wide class of humanities and left-hemispheric cognitive style to natural sciences and technologies” (Stepanov, 2008, p. 305).

Khokhlov (2015) states that a timely consultation allows neuropsychologists to identify features of mental function development and offer a programme of correctional and developmental training. In turn, it significantly benefits the career guidance process (Khokhlov, 2015, p. 28). Provided that there are no developmental disorders, neuropsychologists can determine individual features of the brain responsible for certain activities and give recommendations for further development of cognitive abilities required by some professions. In this case, these specialists consider such indicators as development levels of individual mental functions, as well as the possibility of their integration when carrying out different activities. It especially applies to the development of three structural-functional blocks of the brain (the energy supply of the brain block; the reception, processing and storage block; the programming, regulation and control of complex activities block), functional interhemispheric asymmetry of the brain (Khokhlov, 2015, p. 29).

Thus, neuropsychologists' recommendations can prevent an erroneous choice of the profession. Many prominent researchers have proposed technologies to increase the effectiveness of relevant learning motivation, taking into account the brain functioning principles (Akhutina & Pylaeva, 2008; Miller & Defina, 2010).

In the conclusion, the knowledge of neuropsychological and psychological aspects ensures timely and correct development of cognitive

abilities, without violating the laws of mental functions development. Consequently, it will boost motivation to choose an appropriate professional orientation, increase the range of professional motives and positively affect further personal and professional realization.

The purpose of this article is to present the results of an empirical research aimed at studying the motivational factors of personality in individuals with different levels of professional self-realization.

Literature Overview

The personality is formed and develops throughout life to the extent that a person continues to be included in social and production activities (Petrovsky & Yaroshevsky, 1990, pp. 193–194).

A methodologically important characteristic of today's society is the need for interaction between both personal and professional development as complementary and interdependent processes. In turn, they become for each other either a means or a result contributing to the active transformation of one's inner and outer world. A fundamentally new vision of oneself after the manifestation of subjective life-long activity is based on the establishment, integration and implementation of significant personal qualities and abilities, as well as professional knowledge and skills, in one's professional activities. As noted by Mitina (2002), systematic attempts to optimize "self-creation" lie in modifying one's motivational, intellectual, affective and behavioural structures, which leads to the transformation of external determination into internal (pp. 32–38).

Current globalization makes it somewhat difficult to achieve one's life goals, including professional well-being. This fact encourages various specialists to seek opportunities for full disclosure of their inner potential, professional success, professional self-fulfilment due to motivational characteristics.

Dynamic trends which are determined by goals and objectives of activities act as motivating factors affecting one's determination and activity (Rubinshtein, 2003, p. 519). However, it is impossible to meet all requirements of activities (including professional) without understanding the subject of activity as a source of motivational impulses to solve problems (Petrovsky, & Yaroshevsky, 1990, p. 197).

According to Kokun (2016), personal and professional phenomena of self-realization, self-change, self-development, self-achievement can be combined by one phenomenon called "professional self-realization", which is one of the most important components, and for most people it is the main

form of personal self-improvement (p. 292). Kokun (2016) believes that this phenomenon is a form of self-realization characterized by high-level disclosure of one's professional potential.

The intensification of the most important moments of one's professional growth at different life stages allows one to reveal his or her potential opportunities promoting professional mobility, competitiveness (Zeer, 2005, p. 12) and professional productivity. Professional realization is impossible without including angle of refraction in the consciousness of behaviours (Rubinshtein, 2003, p. 521), as well as without intensifying motives as integrated psychological phenomena, caused by motivation to achieve the goal (Ilyin, 2002, p. 115).

The authors of the article believe that motivation as a set of motives plays the role of an important indicator of one's professional realization. It is the driving force of one's professional activities and determination to solve certain cognitive tasks (Vorobeva, & Pityukov, 2013, pp. 10–11). Motivation can be both internal and external, pushing a person to perform certain professional actions. Intrinsic motivation is associated with a stable striving for a particular goal, with the presence of a dominant that ensures the priority of the profession. This type of motivation triggers the subject's activity in a specific direction, contributes to the creation of conditions in the social environment, which explains its significance. Motivation external to a person is a control mechanism and determines the correction of the processes of self-government, self-regulation of a person (Poletaeva, 2014, p. 30). The characteristics of motivation allow us to conclude that it is a reflection of the internal structure of the subject of professional activity. This is facilitated by the desire and readiness of the individual to perform certain actions in order to satisfy any professional needs.

Directly for our research, a circumstance that determines the fact of the relationship between motivation as a structural education and professional self-realization of an individual is quite significant. Let's imagine it as follows. Any person «enters» the profession as an already formed personality. He defines the attitude towards the profession and towards himself as a professional, self-satisfying the realisation of the necessary professional conditions. At the same time, the process of self-realization of a future professional presupposes a subjective solution to the tasks of a significant increase in personal potential using motives specific to him. It is the set of motives, as constituent elements of the human psyche that reveals the stable psychological formations of the personality and encourages the search for new ways that contribute to the development of subjective activity aimed at mastering new professional knowledge, skills and abilities.

Thus, taking into account the fact that self-realization, self-development, self-actualization in the profession is possible with the satisfaction of needs that contribute to a person's awareness of the complexity degree of solving professional problems, maintaining at the proper level the attitude towards himself as a professional, we assumed that a set of motivational factors induces a person to professional self-realization.

Materials & methods

In an empirical study, psychometrically reliable and valid methods were used to study the structure specifics and motivational factors manifestations of the personality in persons of different professional self-realization level. To study professional self-realisation, the methodology of Kokun (2014) "Questionnaire of professional self-realisation" was used. As the author of the method notes, the phenomenon of self-realization is a systemic phenomenon of a higher order and in the semantic content is very close to such concepts as self-realization, self-actualization, and self-development. Under the concept of "professional self-realization" the questionnaire developer understands a high level of development of the personal potential of a specialist in a particular profession, the development of his abilities related to the profession, the widespread use of professional qualifications, experience, achievements of both his own and other professional specialists (Kokun, 2014, p. 35).

The questionnaire consists of two parts. The first part contains 30 questions and is intended both for measuring the general level of a specialist's professional self-realization, and for assessing the severity of its individual components, including professional self-improvement aimed at increasing professional competence, professionally important qualities. The second part of the questionnaire is aimed at measuring the external signs of professional self-realisation (significant achievements in professional activity). For this, a content analysis of the subject descriptions is used, which freely answer the question: "How does professional activity create opportunities for personal self-realization?" (Kokun, 2014, pp. 35–39).

To study the motivational factors of personality, the test «Motivational profile» was used, authors Richie, & Martin (2004). The proposed test construct is aimed at investigating the essence of motivation, which the authors consider as satisfying basic human needs in the process of work (Richie & Martin, 2004, p. 9).

As conceived by the authors, the test contains 33 tasks, which are litmus for 12 motivational factors (the names of the factors are given below

in the text of the article). For each task, four answer options are offered, each answer must be assessed so that the 11 points given by the test developers are distributed among the four given answer options, i.e. the total would be 11 points. Based on the test results, a motivational profile of a professional's personality is built, which allows you to identify differences in attitude to work, answer the questions: "What motivates a person?", "What aspects of professional activity are the main and secondary motivators?" (Richie & Martin, 2004, pp. 16–27).

The empirical base of the research was the South Ukrainian National Pedagogical University named after K. D. Ushynsky. The psycho-diagnostic survey was attended by full-time and part-time undergraduates of the social and humanitarian faculty of the retraining department in the specialty "Psychology" in the amount of 115 people of both sexes. Master's students, representatives of the personnel retraining department already have the first higher non-psychological education, including professional experience in their specialty.

To achieve the stated goal of the study, quantitative (correlation) and qualitative (profile method) analysis was used.

The study of correlations between indicators of professional self-realisation and personal motivational factors was carried out according to the method of K. Pearson (Anastazi, & Urbina, 2001).

Results & Discussion

The results of the correlation analysis are presented in the form of a constellation in Tabl. 1. Before proceeding to the obtained results interpretation, it is necessary to clarify the symbols of the indicators that are analyzed: 1) indicators of professional self-realisation: S1 – the need for professional improvement, S2 – the presence of their own professional development project, S3 – the prevailing pleasure in one's own professional achievements, S4 – the constant setting of new professional goals, S5 – the formation of one's own «vital professional space», S6 – the achievement of the set professional goals, S7 – the use of professional experience and achievements by others, S8 – disclosure of personal potential and professional abilities, S9 – definition of a high level of creativity in professional activities; 2) indicators of personal motivational factors: M1 – the need for reward, M2 – the need for good working conditions, M3 – the need for clear structuring of work, M4 – the need for social contacts, M5 – the need to form and maintain long-term stable mutual understanding, M6 – the need for recognition, M7 – the need for achievement, M8 – the need for

influence, the desire to lead others, M9 – the need for variety and change, M10 – the need to be creative, M11 – the need for self-improvement, growth and development, M12 – the need for a sense of demand and interesting work.

The visual correlation analysis, presented in Table. 1, clearly demonstrates ambiguous significant relationships ($p \leq 0.01$; $p \leq 0.05$) between most indicators of professional self-realisation and motivational factors of the individual.

The indicator of professional self-realization S1 (the need for professional improvement) negatively correlates ($p \leq 0.01$) with the indicators of motivational factors M2 (the need for good working conditions), M3 (the need for clear structuring of work), M4 (the need for social contacts), M5 (the need to form and maintain long-term stable mutual understanding) and with the M6 factors (the need for recognition) at the level of $p \leq 0.05$ significance.

Table 1. *Significant correlations between indicators of professional self-fulfillment and motivational orientation*

Source: Authors' own conception

Motivation indicators	Indicators of professional self-fulfillment							
	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5	S6	S7	S8
M1						-303**		
M2	-259**				-247*	-291**		-208*
M3	-262**							-278*
M4	-264**			-341**		-183*		-274**
M5	-348**	-281**		-274**				-327**
M6	-211*							
M7							289**	
M8	236*	219*		227*				
M9		303**	223*				238*	284**
M10	258*	311**	336**	293**	321**	239*	291**	395**
M12		385**	384**	420**	354**		398**	420**

Note. 1) commas and zeros are not specified; 2) mark ** - $p \leq 0.01$; 3) * - $p \leq 0.05$.

Also, this indicator positively correlates ($p \leq 0.05$) with motivational factors M8 (the need for influence, the desire to lead others) and M10 (the need to be creative). The data obtained can be interpreted as follows. Professional self-realisation, in terms of the need for improvement as a professional, is not always dictated by the needs for good working conditions, a comfortable environment (M2); the need for structuring work,

setting rules and directives for performing work (M3); the needs of communication with a wide range of people, close ties with colleagues (M4); needs to form and maintain long-term, close, stable relationships with colleagues at work (M5); needs for sympathy for others, attention from other people (M6). However, the need for professional self-realization directly (linearly) depends on the actualization of such needs as: assertiveness in influence and power, the desire to lead others, persistence in the pursuit of competition (M8); manifestation of inquisitiveness, curiosity, and not trivial thinking, the desire to be creative, analyzing, thinking worker, open to new ideas (10).

Self-realisation indicator S2 (having a project of one's own professional development) positively correlates ($p \leq 0.01$) with such motivational factors as: M9 (the need for variety and change), M10 (the need to be creative), M12 (the need for a sense of being in demand and interesting work) and at the level of $p \leq 0.05$ significance with a factor M8 (need for influence, desire to lead others). In addition, this indicator negatively correlates ($p \leq 0.01$) with the M5 factor (the need to form and maintain long-term stable mutual understanding). These results can be explained by the fact that professional self-realization always presupposes some kind of project, plan, scenario of actions regarding professional development, this requires certain motivators, namely: comparing oneself with other people to influence them, the desire to manage and lead them (M8); the need for variety, change, readiness for action (M9); need for work filled with meaning and meaning, with an element of social utility (M12). However, for a project of professional self-development, there is no need to actualize the need to form and maintain closer contacts with others (M5).

Self-realisation indicator S3 (prevailing pleasure in one's own professional achievements) positively correlates ($p \leq 0.05$) with the motivational factor M9 (the need for variety and change), as well as with factors ($p \leq 0.01$) the need to be creative (M10) and the need for feeling demand and interesting work (M12). In the process of professional self-realization, in order to stimulate the enjoyment of one's own achievements, such motivators are needed as: avoidance of routine and boredom through diversity and the desire for change (M9); be a creative worker (M10); to be in demand in interesting socially useful work (M12).

Self-realization indicator S4 (constant setting of new professional goals) negatively correlates with motivational factors M4 (need for social contacts), M5 (need to form and maintain long-term stable mutual understanding) and positively ($p \leq 0.01$) with factors: M10 (need to be creative), M12 (the need for a sense of being in demand and interesting

work) and at the $p \leq 0.05$ level of significance with the M8 factor (the need for influence, the desire to lead others). Indeed, for setting new professional goals, the most important motivators are: competitive assertiveness, the need for power (M8); creativity, openness to new ideas (M10); professional activity filled with meaning and value of usefulness to society (M12). Along with this, for the setting and implementation of professional goals, motivation and desire to work with other people and have a wide range of social contacts are not so important (M4); form and maintain long-term stable relationships (M5).

Self-realisation indicator S5 (formation of one's own "vital professional space") positively correlates ($p \leq 0.01$) with motivational factors M10 (the need to be creative), M12 (the need for a feeling of being in demand and interesting work) and negatively ($p \leq 0.05$) with factor M2 (the need for good working conditions). The results obtained empirically confirm the fact that in the process of professional self-realization, an important component is the formation of one's own vital professional space, and for this process, important motivators are: openness to new things, rejection of trivial thinking, creativity (M10); the need for work filled with meaning, meaning and utility (M12). The motive for good working conditions and a comfortable environment is leveled out and becomes insignificant (M2).

The indicator of motivational self-realisation S6 (achievement of the set professional goals) negatively correlates ($p \leq 0.01$) with the motivational factors M1 (the need for reward), M2 (the need for good working conditions) and at the $p \leq 0.05$ level of significance with the factor M4 (need for social contacts). This indicator is also positively associated ($p \leq 0.05$) with the motivational factor M10 (the need to be creative). To achieve the set goals of the process of professional self-realization, the main motivator is the need to be creative, creative, to move away from the standard "flare" in professional activity (M10). It is also interesting that for the process of self-realization in achieving the set professional goal, motivators become unimportant: the presence of high wages, i.e. material remuneration, to have a job with a good set of benefits and allowances (M1); good, comfortable working conditions (M2); professional environment, striving for a team, working with other people (M4).

Self-realisation indicator S7 (the use of professional experience and achievements by others) and motivational factors are only positively related. Professional self-realisation correlates ($p \leq 0.01$) with motivational factors M7 (the need for achievement), M10 (the need to be creative), M12 (the need for a sense of being in demand and interesting work) and at the $p \leq 0.05$ significance level with the factor M9 (the need for variety and change). In

professional self-realization, it is very important to use the accumulated personal life and professional experience, as well as knowledge of the achievements of other specialists, therefore, the following become the dominant motivators: the need to set bold complex goals for oneself and achieve them, to conquer difficult, promising frontiers (M7); always be in a state of elation, readiness for action, change (M9); to produce new, creative and creative ideas acceptable for professional implementation (M10); feel in demand at work (M12).

And finally, the indicator of professional self-realisation S8 (disclosure of personal potential and professional abilities) negatively correlates with motivational factors ($p \leq 0.05$) M2 (the need for good working conditions), M3 (the need for clear structuring of work) and with factors M4 (the need in social contacts), M5 (the need to form and maintain long-term stable mutual understanding) at $p \leq 0.05$ level of significance. This indicator of self-realisation also positively correlates ($p \leq 0.01$) with factors M9 (the need for variety and change), M10 (the need to be creative) and M12 (the need for a sense of being in demand and interesting work). As we can see from the results of the obtained correlations in the process of professional self-realization, the opportunity to reveal personal potential and professional abilities is important; important motivators that stimulate this process are: the need for diversity, changes (M9); the need for creativity, inquisitiveness, curiosity, creative thinking (M10); the need for interesting work, an element of social utility (M12). However, as we can see, at the stage of disclosing one's professional potential, such needs are leveled as: a comfortable professional environment and good working conditions (M2); clear structuring, i.e. the establishment of rules and directives for the performance of work, professional requirements, the presence of feedback, allowing you to judge the results of your work (M3); communication with a wide range of people, the presence of social contacts (close ties with colleagues) (M4); the need for stability and trust in relationships with colleagues (M5).

Thus, the discovered and analyzed both positive and negative correlations between the indicators of professional self-realisation and the motivational factors of the personality clearly demonstrate the statistical patterns in the manifestation of the properties of the studied phenomena. Professional self-realization is activated by a certain set of motivational factors of the personality, in other words, for the effective development of the process of professional self-realisation, motivating forces are needed - motivators, in our case, motivational factors of the personality.

The obtained statistical data on the relationship of phenomena allow us to proceed to a discussion of the results of qualitative analysis. It is

important to note that this type of analysis makes it possible not only to single out groups of subjects differing in the level of severity of indicators of professional self-realisation, but to analyze the individual psychological characteristics of the motivational structure in each of the selected group.

The percentile method was used to identify groups of subjects with high and low levels of professional self-realization (Burlachuk, 2002). Using this method, two groups of subjects were obtained; the results are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. *Distribution of the surveyed according to the criterion of professional self-realization*

Source: Authors' own conception

Designations	Number of the surveyed (n=115)	%
Group SR+	16	13,9
Group SR–	13	11,3

Note: 1) group SR + - surveyed respondents with high values of indicators of professional self-realization; 2) group SR – - surveyed respondents with low values of indicators of professional self-realization.

Table 1 shows that the first group included 16 surveyed, which amounted to 13.9% of the total number of respondents. The second group included 13 people, which amounted to 11.3% of the total number of respondents. The remaining 86 participants in psycho-diagnostic testing did not participate in further analysis, since their results determine the “statistical norm corridor”.

On the basis of the test results “Motivational profile” in the selected groups of subjects, the profiles of the structure of the motivational factors of personality were built, which are shown in Fig. 1.

Each value of a specific motivational factor is an arithmetic mean that indicates a high or low level of the parameter expressed in percentile.

The results of statistical values of the reliability of differences according to the Student's t-test in the groups that are analyzed are presented in Table 3. Visual analysis and the values of the Student's t-test clearly demonstrate individual psychological differences in the configuration of the graphs and structures of the motivational factors of the personality of the analyzed groups.

Fig. 1. Profiles of the personal motivational factors structure, group representatives with high and low levels of professional self-realization

Source: Authors' own conception

Note: 1) indicators group SR + - surveyed respondents, with high values of indicators of professional self-realization; 2) SR- group - surveyed respondents with low values of indicators of professional self-realization; 2) indicators of personal motivational factors: M1 – the need for reward, M2 – the need for good working conditions, M3 – the need for clear structuring of work, M4 – the need for social contacts, M5 – the need to form and maintain long-term stable mutual understanding, M6 – the need for recognition, M7 – the need for achievement, M8 – the need for influence, the desire to lead others, M9 – the need for variety and change, M10 – the need to be creative, M11 – the need for self-improvement, growth and development, M12 – the need for a sense of demand and interesting work.

Table 3. Statistical values of Student's t-test between the same motivational factors of personality

Source: Authors' own conception

Student's t-test	Indicators of professional self-realisation (n=115)						
	M2	M4	M5	M6	M10	M11	M12
	2,13**	-2,1**	-2,1**	2,27**	1,61*	6,06***	6,81***

The differences were revealed:

- between the motivational factors of the same type – the need for good working conditions (M2), the need for social contacts (M4), the need to form and maintain long-term stable mutual understanding (M5) towards the group of respondents with low values of indicators of professional self-realization;

- between the motivational factors of the same type – the need for recognition (M6), the need to be creative (M10), the need for self-improvement, growth and development (M11), the need for a sense of demand and interesting work (M12) towards the group of respondents with high values of professional self-realization.

Based on the empirical data obtained, psychological portraits of the surveyed respondents were compiled. So, for respondents, representatives of a group with high values of indicators of professional self-realization, the dominant motivators are the need to gain recognition from other people, in particular, that others appreciate the merits, achievements and successes of an individual. Such respondents are concerned about the attention from colleagues, they are not indifferent to the sympathy of others and good social relationships and it is also important for them to realize a sense of their own worth. In addition, important motivators are the need for improvement, growth and development as a person, the need for a sense of demand for interesting socially useful work. For professional self-realization, such individuals are not important motivators such as having good working conditions and a comfortable environment, they are not picky in communication, there is no expressed need for a wide range of close, trusting contacts and relationships, they are communicatively self-sufficient and adaptive, and they already have perfected social skills.

For respondents, representatives of the group with low values of indicators of professional self-realization, the dominant motivators are the need for high wages and material remuneration; desire to have a job with a good set of benefits and allowances. This need reveals a tendency to change in the process of working life; an increase in resource costs leads to an increase in the importance of this need (for example, the emergence of new family obligations, the presence of debts, additional or complex financial obligations). For a person with a low need for professional self-fulfillment, a significant motivator is also an urgent need for social contacts, the need to form and maintain long-term, stable relationships, which manifests itself in communication with a wide range of people, the desire to establish close contacts regardless of the system of relationships in the team (for example, conflict, enemy, frustrating), the most important thing for such people is to

perform production operations, to work with others. For such respondents, the need for independence, improvement, growth and development as a person, professional relevance is uncharacteristic.

Conclusions

In general, the results obtained indicate that the pivotal factor of professional self-realization is a combination of internal and external motives.

Statistical analysis confirmed that the quantitative and qualitative combination of the motivational factors of the personality determine the effectiveness of the process of professional self-realization.

Statistically significant differences were revealed in the structure of motivational factors in the groups of respondents, differing in the level of professional self-realization. In the group of respondents with a low level of professional self-realization, motivators dominate - the need for reward and social contacts, the motivators of the need to be creative, to improve, to be in demand and to have an interesting job are not expressed. In the group of respondents with a high level of professional self-realization, motivators dominate - the need to be creative, to improve oneself in the profession, to feel in demand, to have an interesting job, at the same time in this group, the motivators of the need for good working conditions and for clear structuring of work are reduced.

The presented psychological portraits explain the individual psychological characteristics in the manifestation of motivational factors in the groups of respondents that are being studied.

The results obtained do not exhaust all aspects of the problem under study. A prospect for further scientific research may be the search for a wider range of motivational properties of a person striving for professional self-fulfillment, as well as taking into account age and gender differences.

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